

THE IMPORTANCE OF MUSEUMS IN ENRICHING THE SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL VALUES OF THE POPULATION, EDUCATING THE YOUNG GENERATION IN THE SPIRIT OF LOVE AND LOYALTY TO THE FATHERLAND

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Annotating - The article emphasizes the importance, history, and theoretical foundations of museums in enriching the world of spiritual and educational values of the population, educating the young generation in the spirit of love and loyalty to the Motherland.

Key words: museum, tourism, culture, heritage, enlightenment, standard of living, quality of life.

Great attention has been paid to restoration of our national tradition and values, in-depth study of our rich heritage, and wide promotion of its essence and importance among our people, especially among the youth. In order to preserve and enrich our national traditions, 11 new museums, 2 theaters, 28 children's music and art schools, 5 universities, including the University of Journalism and Mass Communications of Uzbekistan, were established to train the new generation of journalists. Here we focus on an important number. The amount of state support for culture and art increased 5 times compared to 2017, and in 2023 more than 712 billion soums were allocated for these directions. The spirituality of any people or nation cannot be imagined without its history and national values. Therefore, cultural and historical monuments of our ancient land, unique artifacts, thousands of years old finds and objects, rare manuscripts, which contributed an incomparable share to the world civilization, are unique examples of not only our nation's, but also the world's heritage.

To further improve the system of museums formed in the territory of Uzbekistan, to increase their place in the spiritual and moral maturity of the people, to carefully preserve, study, enrich, take out and promote the rich history of our nation, the steps of our independence preserved in the museum funds, First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov (On January 12, 1998 (PF-1913) the Decree "On radical improvement and improvement of the activities of museums" was adopted.

According to the decree, the Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Academy of Arts and the State Press Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan shall increase the museology culture of the population of our country, make them aware of our heritage and values, publish the scientific works of experts and museum employees in the field of museology, and promote achievements in this field within three months in order to improve the professional qualifications of museum employees. Once, ambitious plans were set, such as the establishment of a scientific-practical, spiritual-educational, color magazine "Mozidan Sado" to be published in Uzbek, English and Russian languages. Of course, this decree became a

historical document in bringing the activities of museums to high levels in our country.

The State Program of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the Implementation of the Strategy of Actions on the Five Priority Areas of the Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 in the "Year of Communication with the People and Human Interests", approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev No. PF-4947 of February 7, 2017 The Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan in connection with the implementation of the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures for the further development and improvement of the sphere of culture and art" of May 31, 2017 No. - made a decision on approving the program of events.

In the decision, the new concepts of state museums to be developed, safe storage of museum objects, creation of favorable conditions for visitors, especially for disabled people, development of tourist services, architecture-planning, interior, design and landscape solutions, drawing a sketch of each museum building. It is decided to approve the project based on the direction and content of the museum.

The fact that tourism development issues are included in all decisions of our government requires the organization of new directions and new types of tourism in national tourism. That is, museology faced the social, economic and political problems of modernity. The authors of the new museum concept are introducing new methods of communication with the community in the museum. In modern life, it is necessary to implement wider programs that help museums to take an active part in the life of the society, departing from their traditional tasks and functions. One of such broad programs is the creation of a new type of science and practice in the national tourism of our country - "Museology in Tourism". Taking into account the urgency of this issue, the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of Uzbekistan introduced the subject "Museology in Tourism" to the State Education Standards.

The use of museums in our country is important in the development of tourism in our republic. Especially in the social and educational life of our people, in the culturally mature education of the young generation, in the formation of the expansion of the scope of human knowledge, increasing the use of our museums in tourism remains one of the most urgent problems.

In the Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev "On measures for the innovative development of the sphere of culture and art in the Republic of Uzbekistan" (Tashkent, August 26, 2018) the following is defined:

- creation of an infrastructure designed for the population, first of all for the young generation, allowing to view museum exhibits by using the Internet, widely introducing innovative information technologies to the activities of museums and creating digital forms of museum exhibits;

- ensuring the full integration of museums into the social space in order to popularize and promote the cultural and historical heritage of our country;

- wide use of inclusive methods of providing services and providing comfort to persons with limited capabilities, elderly visitors, children of preschool age and accompanying persons in museums;

This Decision starts the development of museums in our country. First of all, the national tourism of our country should contribute its effective scientific and practical research and work to the development. Organization and development of the use of museums in national tourism should be accelerated. Secondly, in recent years in our country, the interest and visits of our people, especially the younger generation, to museums, and the initiative to organize these visits, and at the same time, the interest of the peoples of the world, international tourists, and the heads of state who have visited our country, are increasing year by year. Because Uzbekistan has internationally known and famous museums. Therefore, future specialists in tourism education should master the mechanisms of organizing and developing the use of museums in tourism through the science of "Museology in Tourism".

The wealth of the peoples living in Central Asia was first plundered by the armies of Alexander the Great in the 4th century BC. When they open the tomb of King Vishtasp in a temple in the ancient city of Tos, instead of the riches they expect, they find the Avesta written on skin. Angry, Alexander orders it to be burned. Thus, the first copy of the great "Avesta" was destroyed.

All the wealth of the peoples who lived in Central Asia, especially the world's unparalleled libraries, were burned during the invasion of Genghis Khan. Even during the Arab invasion, unparalleled libraries were destroyed. The establishment of the independent Somani state in Central Asia (9th century) made a fundamental change in this regard. During this period, in addition to the wealth of the palace, large libraries and archives were established. According to history, there were many rare books created by mankind in the libraries of Bukhara and Shiraz emirates in the 10th century.

Muhammad Ghaznavi, the founder of the Ghaznavid dynasty, also collected many books. Khorezmshah Muhammad did great things for the development of the country. He built beautiful palaces, castles, mausoleums. Rare material and spiritual wealth was accumulated, but these unique art and cultural monuments, the whole city was lost due to the occupation of the Mongol invaders. Libraries were burned, cultural life retreated for 100 years. After 150 years, science and culture began to develop again in Central Asia. In particular, the creation of a unified centralized state by Amir Timur and the capitalization of Samarkand led to the accumulation of great wealth. Architectural monuments, mausoleums, mosque-madrasas, palaces were built.

Amir Timur brought to Samarkand ancient manuscripts, correspondence and embassy documents of khans and emirs, the holy book of the Muslim world, "Uthman's Qur'an", from the conquered countries. He founded the world-famous Timur Library. Timur's beloved grandson, Mirzo Ulug'bek, the great astronomer of the East, enriched this library. All Timurid rulers made a great contribution to the development of culture.

According to information, Alisher Navoi had a very large, rare, personal library rich in manuscripts. Historian Khondamir, artist Behzod and other scholars

used this library. In Bukhara-Khiva khanates, it was customary to build many palaces and private libraries with a collection of rare manuscripts.

Khan of Khiva Muhammed Rahim II (1865-1910, a famous poet under the pseudonym Feruz) built a library and enriched it with rare manuscripts brought from all over the world. First in Central Asia, lithography was established in Khiva, and publishing art was developed. In the 19th century, the Khanate of Khiva became world famous for its treasure of books. Here the manuscripts in Arabic, Persian-Tajik languages are translated into Uzbek.

Kokan khanate also had a rich library and rare manuscripts. During this period, there were book lovers in the big cities of Central Asia, Fergana, Bukhara, Kokan, Tashkent and other cities, who spent a lot of money and bought rare manuscripts. For example, in Tashkent, the private collection of manuscripts of Jorabek (killed in 1906) was famous. The libraries of Baqijan Bai, Qazi Muhyiddin, Dukchi Eshon in Andijan, the library of Qazi Sharifjan Mahzun Zia, who lived in Bukhara, and the manuscripts in it were famous for their rarity and antiquity. , performed in accordance with Islamic traditions.

The encyclopedic and royal works of the great scholars of Central Asia were translated into Latin in European countries from the 12th century, and made a great contribution to the development of world science. In Eastern countries, these masterpieces became the golden fund of libraries. European scientists and ruling circles have been trying to capture the history, culture and cultural monuments of the peoples of Central Asia for a long time. In the later period, it was thought that not only the manuscripts of the earthly authors, but also the works of the great thinkers of the East, whose names are known but not found, could come from Central Asia.

Their predictions turned out to be correct, and as a result of their consistent actions, the spiritual treasures of Central Asia became the property of the European-Asian countries. These things were done in different ways: these riches were given as gifts to the ambassadors who came to the khanate, they began to go to foreign countries through the actions of merchants, tourists who came on purpose, middlemen, and because of invasions.

For example: in 1740, Nadirshah, the horn of Iran, invaded Central Asia and took many relics from the mausoleum of Amir Temur: a jade stone over Temur's grave, a gold-handled sword and shields of the sahibqiran placed on the mausoleum, and a Koran placed on the grave were taken away among the countless loots captured from Samarkand. But Timur quickly returns his tombstone because it broke on the way.

In 1831-1833, the lieutenant of the East India Company, Alexander Burns, lived in Bukhara, collected ancient gold and silver coins and built a collection of more than 200 rare numismatics and presented them to the British Museum. Now this collection is priceless. In this robbery, the Russian Empire carried out a separate, large-scale "research".

Director of the Museum of Asia in St. Petersburg, orientalist H. D. In 1834, Fran compiled a "Chronological List of One Hundred Works" of Eastern Authors, which can be found in Central Asia. The Orenburg customs office was ordered to send merchants and to send the specified manuscripts to Petersburg, and this task was

carried out more than expected, and the geography of the history of the peoples of the Near and Middle East. valuable manuscripts began to flow to Petersburg. This was the first stage of removal of the material and spiritual monuments of Central Asia. Turkestan monuments began to appear in the libraries of the royal palaces of European countries and Russia. In 1853, during the capture of the White Mosque fortress by the Russian troops, our material and spiritual treasures were brutally looted by the Russian troops.

Since 1869, planned measures of looting have been developed. Soldier-officers were given a letter of recommendation written in Petersburg, and it was indicated what things they should pay attention to. Main target: Manuscripts, documents, coins, seals, examples of applied art, antiques, products of local artisans, carpets, copper carvings, rare saddles and harnesses, jewelry, especially with studs and precious stones, from the cities and khanates of Turkestan. decorated swords, daggers, knives and other objects made of precious metals were to be sent to museums and libraries in St. Petersburg.

Military chiefs and officials did not forget to collect these valuable monuments. In 1869, in Samarkand, the first general-governor of Turkestan K. P. Von Kaufman (1867-1882y) sent the sacred book of the Muslim world, the 7th century Kufa manuscript monument "Othman's Qur'an" to the Emperor of Petersburg. In 1870, 97 volumes of ancient manuscripts were seized from places belonging to Shahrizabz and Kitab begs during a military campaign under the pretext of suppressing the uprising of citizens of Bukhara emir.

The collection of cultural and spiritual monuments on a scientific basis was very well organized before the march to Khiva Khanate in 1873. The Russian Geographical Society in St. Petersburg took the lead in this work. The great Oriental scholar P. I. Lerkh developed an excellent program on what to pay attention to and collect in the Khanate and sent it to Turkestan. The program, that is, the "Instruction", was published by typography and distributed to soldiers and officers. "In a special section of the "Instruction", the collection of archival documents, gold, silver coins and manuscript books was specially noted. . It is also indicated that it should be taken from the above monuments, courthouses, mosque-madrassa and houses. Abu Raikhan Beruni, A. Necessity of having the manuscripts of Navoi and other thinkers is indicated. The sending of written manuscripts and antiques to St. Petersburg will be administratively entrusted to the oriental scientist A.L. Kun, the honorary adviser of the Governor General of Turkestan. Ways to motivate soldiers and officers will be shown.

At this time, Khiva Khan hastily fled, and the palace was left in the hands of the invaders. The Khan's palace and its treasures were looted, manuscripts and documents were sent to the Petersburg Imperial Library (now the Petersburg State Library named after S. Shchedrin). In 1874, the throne of the Khan of Khiva was handed over to the armory in Moscow. The Russian scientist who scientifically described this throne V. V. Stasov says: "This throne is the pinnacle of skill of Khiva craftsmen, that is, a unique product of the art of painting flowers on metal."

Among the valuable spoils taken from the Khan's palace were 200 coins, 25 pounds of gold and silver, the seal of the Khan, more than 200 ancient coins,

innumerable precious stones and gold jewelry and clothing. These items were sent to St. Petersburg and Moscow museums, the Hermitage, the Tsarskoselsky Arsenal, the Moscow Polytechnic Museum, the Museum of Ethnography and other places. These were masterpieces of art brought from all over the world.

It consisted of innumerable Chinese porcelain vessels, Iranian and Turkmen silk carpets, Kashmiri shawls, magnificent robes and weapons, and innumerable jewels. There are more than 1,000 Chinese porcelain items dating back to the XVII-XVIII-XIX centuries, which became a prey for Russian officers.

In 1875-1876, there was a march to Kokhan, the khanate was abolished, the treasure of the khanate, manuscripts, valuable copper, gold, silver items, and weapons were sent to Petersburg. Until now, copper and jewelry from Kokan are displayed in the exhibitions of major museums - the Hermitage, the British Museum and other museums. Thus, at the expense of the spilled blood of the peoples of Central Asia, 5 administrative regions were formed on the land of Turkestan: Syrdarya, Zarafshan (Samarkand), Ferghana, Trans-Caspian region, Ettisuv and became dependent on the governor-general and became a full-fledged colony of Russia. Bukhara and Khiva remained khanates of the Russian Empire. In the country, the demi-tsar Turkestan was the governor-general, who had unlimited powers.

Now a new task was to master the vast territory of Central Asia, to turn it into a stronghold of Tsarism in the East, a source of wealth, to thoroughly study the land, that is, to study the land's underground and surface resources, flora and fauna, history, ethnography. In this regard, a large program was developed: it was intended to study and master Turkestan's ancient history, material and spiritual monuments, geography, underground and surface resources, nature, animal world, customs, and lifestyle on a large scale. For this purpose, the governor-general the state of honorary advisers was established and scholars of eastern history were recruited to these positions. Orientalists from St. Petersburg came to Central Asia on permanent and long-term business trips and conducted comprehensive investigations with the help of local collectors and orientalists. They started with archeological excavations and unique mausoleums and madrasahs. As a result of these works, ancient rare monuments and valuable resources were collected at their disposal. These rare resources will be sent to St. Petersburg museums and libraries.

They went to all the cities of Turkestan with the authority of the governor-general and collected the personal collections of khan's palaces, madrasahs, mosques, treasury and merchants, material and cultural monuments, ancient rare manuscripts, sorted them and sent them to the archaeological commission in St. Petersburg, the Asian Museum and the Imperial Library. In addition to these, more than 15 scientific societies and circles worked in Turkestan from 1867 to 1917 for this purpose.

In 1895, a circle of archaeologists, ethnographers and anthropologists was established in Tashkent, headed by Nikolay Petrovich Ostroumov. The main task of the club was to collect and study monuments embodying the rich culture and history of the country. In this work, cooperation was established with the Society of Imperial Archaeologists in St. Petersburg. The circle informed the center about the collected monuments and sent the monuments to St. Petersburg on the recommendation of the people in the center.

In 1898, the library of Dukchi Eshon, the leader of the Andijan rebellion, was confiscated. 194 rare manuscripts in it were quickly sent to Petersburg. There were 3 other working groups who were enthusiastic about sending the treasures of Turkestan to the center, they were fans of local amateur monuments. They were the intellectuals of the country, officials of the Russian administration and senior and junior military officials.

Figures of Russian history relied on local fans in their scientific and relic-collecting work in Turkestan. For example: Mirza Kasimov from Samarkand, merchant Akrom Askarov from Tashkent, Mirza Abdulla Bukhari from Samarkand, ethnographer Shohimardon Ibrohimov, Abu Said Makhsum from Samarkand, archaeologist Olim Turdi Mirgiyosov and others. In addition to these, countless experts from St. Petersburg and Moscow museums often came to the country and took away countless monuments.

Thus, such an attractive, legendary land hastened the Russian rulers. The work of "scientific investigation" has developed everywhere in the country. The tsarist government did not allow the people of Turkistan to realize themselves nationally, because they believed that spreading historical knowledge among them and drawing their attention to the value of ancient monuments would undermine the colonial policy of tsarism. But Czarism, which considered Central Asia as its colonial property, well understood the need to study Turkestan on a scientific basis in order to absorb its incomparable wealth.

Scientific societies, research scientists of the Turkestan region, some individuals, some institutions filled with wonderful collections related to mineralogy, zoology, numismatics, ethnography, flora, fauna of the Turkestan region. Now a sorting center was needed to unite the scattered collections and send them to St. Petersburg. The most suitable Center for this purpose is a museum, and the question of establishing a museum in the country was raised. Including A. P. Fedchenko wrote in the information he prepared for the Governor General of Turkestan that "in order to successfully develop Turkestan, it is necessary to get to know it thoroughly, and the museum is the best tool for this."

Thus, A. P. Fedchenko, I. V. Mushketov, V. F. Oshanin, V. V. Barthold and others were the initiators of the construction of museums in Turkestan. In 1876, the first Tashkent Museum (now the State Museum of the History of Uzbekistan) was opened. Since then, the existence of the main museum in Central Asia was officially recognized. In 1896, in Samarkand, in 1898, in Ettisuv, in 1899, the museums of Fergana and Trans-Caspian (Ashkhabot) were established.

As for the content of the expositions, one of its main tasks was to honor the victories of the tsarist weapon in Central Asia, the "combat" of the Russian generals and officers in the conquest of Turkestan was praised, and countless portraits of them were shown. Without explanatory texts in local languages, local residents needed brief explanations to see and understand the museum. In general, the colonial administration used museum expositions to promote the ideas of the ruling metropolis. In this case, the Russian bourgeoisie, merchants and corchalans, were trying to create publicity to show off their achievements in exploiting the natural resources of the colony and thereby monetize their products.

From the middle of the 19th century, ethnographic museums were established and during this period, ethnography is also formed as a science. We will briefly touch upon the formation and development of the first museums in our country, Uzbekistan. In 1876, the Museum of Turkestan was established in Tashkent (July 12). The museum was entrusted to the statistical committee, and from 1877 it was managed by the committee of members of the Turkestan department. N.A. Maev, the former editor of *Turkestanskoe vedomosti* newspaper, was appointed as the director of the museum.

The museum stayed in his house until 1878 due to the lack of a building. In February 1919, the museum was moved to a part of the "white house", the residence of the General Governor of Turkestan. In the next period, the museum was named after the writer Oybek. In the fund of the Museum of the History of the Peoples of Uzbekistan, there are up to 52,000 items from archaeological materials, more than 43,000 coins, medals and other coins from numismatics, and more than 1,800 memorial items from ethnography.

The number of photographs, negatives and documents in the museum card file and archive exceeds 100,000. (1978) The museum was reorganized on the basis of the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 21, 1992, No. 203. It was named the State Museum of the History of Uzbekistan. The total area is 2,000 m² and 12,000 exhibits are located. In addition to the Turkestan Museum, the Fergana Regional Museum was opened in 1895, and it was initially called the city's folk museum. On June 21, 1896 in Samarkand, the structure of the exposition of the "Samarkand Statistics Committee Museum" (now the Museum of Culture and Art History of Uz. R.) was the usual art camera, in which various materials were collected.

A. Askarov from Russian amateur collectors (A.I. Dobrosmyslov, N.S. Likoshin, N.P. Ostroumov, A.L. Vyatkin, N.N. Karamzin, local representatives Mirzo Bukhori, Mirzo Kasimov) played a great role in filling the museums. On December 10, 1918, the Decree on the accounting and preservation of museums and collections is published. On August 20, 1919, the "Regulation on the People's Museum of Turkestan" was approved. In 1943, this museum was transferred to the UzFA system.

In 1920, the Museum of Local History of Namangan City, in 1923, the Museum of History and Local History of Bukhara Province, and in 1934, the Museum of Local History of Chirchik City was established. In 1913, there were 3 museums in the territory of present-day Uzbekistan. In 1924, the number was 8, in 1940 - 17, and in the late 70s - 27.

There are 510 museums in large and small cities and districts of our independent Uzbekistan. Karakalpakstan State Local History Museum was established in Tortkol in 1929. Academicians S.F. Oldenberg, A. Samoylovich, correspondent member of the academy S.P. Tolinsky and scientists from Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan helped in this. In the early 1930s, graduates of Moscow University, N.A. Baskakov, N.V. Torchinskaya, and later, doctor of philology, professor Kalli Ayimbetov, took an active part in the work of the museum. Scientists Melkov, Morozova, S.P. Tolstov, T. Zhdanko and others contributed to filling the exhibits of this museum in later periods. In 1944, the museum was moved from Tortkol to the

city of Nukus. In 1965, it was moved to the current building. The museum fund has more than 50,000 exhibits. Karakalpakstan State Art Museum was opened in 1966.

In museological literature, the first period of the development of museum work in Uzbekistan (1917-1923) was determined by the activities of the committees for the protection and preservation of ancient and art monuments (Turkkomstaris, Sredazkomstaris, Uzkomstaris).

The second period (1923-1930) of the organization of collected materials, identification of the main types of museums (central, regional, local) according to their importance set a certain limit in the collection of materials. The third period (1930-1941), the period before the war, had a reconstructive character. Museum branches have expanded. During this period, in 1933, the first republican conference of museum employees was convened in Tashkent to discuss the issue of determining the main directions for the further development of the museum's work.

The fourth period corresponds to the years of the Patriotic War (1941-1945). Expositions representing the republic's participation in the war were created,

the museum is important in educating the people in the spirit of courage and patriotism

it happened. Permanent and traveling exhibitions are organized. Museum exhibits were not only a source of scientific research, but also served practical purposes.

Fifth period. 1946-1964 corresponds to the period of post-war reconstruction. The ideas of the totalitarian system dominated the activities of the museums in the period before independence, and this made the work of introducing the masterpieces of national values to the world through the museum a central focus. It was only because of our independence that restrictions were put to an end. Museums showing our nationality and identity have appeared. For example: State Museum of Timurids (October 18, 1996), Olympic Fame Museum (September 1, 1996), etc.

International Council of Museums (ICOM) under UNESCO introduces the experiences of world museums. Its main task:

a) coordinating the work of museums and certain specialists in museology and developing their international cooperation;

b) to involve all museums in the world and some specialists in museology to work in cooperation with international and cultural-educational organizations;

c) strengthening mutual acquaintance and cooperation between peoples.

All these tasks include international seminars on museology, organizing conferences, scientific trips and conducting research done by The General Assembly, the supreme body of the International Museum Council, is convened once in 3 years.

The main social functions of any museum will be:

- First, the scientific documentary function. In this case, the museum performs the service of scientific documentation of any event, process, development laws of nature and society;

- Second, the protection function. This is the function of museums to protect cultural and historical monuments in the interests of national and world culture;

- Thirdly, research function. In this, the museum functions as a special center of scientific research;

- Fourthly, educational function. This determines the role of museums during the formation of a social democratic society in the current era.

Museums are protected by law. On the other hand, museums take legal, scientific and protection responsibility of monuments before the state and society. The function of scientific documentation is primarily based on museum objects. In this case, items are divided into special funds and documented. The fund consists of sources of various types and types. The research function is also based on museum objects. It is studied as the first source. According to it, economic, political, social and cultural development processes are studied. The educational and educational function is also of great importance. This is because the museum is aimed at the general public.

Here, people not only get knowledge, but also get aesthetic wealth and form their own thinking. Of course, museum expositions and exhibitions play an important role in this. Museums form a huge closed system that develops in terms of content. This system includes museums of various profiles and types, they are called museum networks. Its formation is influenced by social requirements, development of science and art, etc. The quality of museum networks depends on the improvement of museum sectors.

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